

MWE-LEX 2020

**Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Electronic
Lexicons**

Proceedings of the Workshop

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Barcelona, Spain (Online)

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Introduction

The Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Electronic Lexicons (MWE-LEX 2020)¹ took place in an online format on December 13, 2020 in conjunction with COLING 2020.

This was the 16th edition of the Workshop on Multiword Expressions (MWE 2020). The event was organized and sponsored by the Special Interest Group on the Lexicon (SIGLEX)² of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL) and by ELEXIS³ - European Lexicographic Infrastructure.

The joint MWE-LEX workshop addressed two domains – multiword expressions and (electronic) lexicons – with partly overlapping communities and research interests, but divergent practices and terminologies.

Multiword expressions (MWEs) are word combinations, such as in *the middle of nowhere*, *hot dog*, *to make a decision* or *to kick the bucket*, displaying lexical, syntactic, semantic, pragmatic and/or statistical idiosyncrasies. Because of their unpredictable behavior, notably their non-compositional semantics, MWEs pose problems in linguistic modelling (e.g. treebank annotation, grammar engineering), NLP pipelines (notably when orchestrated with parsing), and end-user applications (e.g. information extraction).

Because MWE-hood is a largely lexical phenomenon, appropriately built electronic MWE lexicons turn out to be quite important for NLP. Large standardised multilingual, possibly interconnected, NLP-oriented MWE lexicons prove indispensable for NLP tasks such as MWE identification, due to its critical sensitivity to unseen data. But the development of such lexicons is challenging and calls for tools which would leverage, on the one hand, MWEs encoded in pre-existing NLP-unaware lexicons and, on the other hand, automatic MWE discovery in large non-annotated corpora.

In order to allow better convergence and scientific innovation within these two largely complementary scientific communities, we called for papers on joint topics on MWEs and e-lexicons, on the one hand, and on MWE-specific topics, on the other hand.

Joint topics on MWEs and e-lexicons

- Extracting and enriching MWE lists from traditional human-readable lexicons for NLP use
- Formats for NLP-applicable MWE lexicons
- Interlinking MWE lexicons with other language resources
- Using MWE lexicons in NLP tasks (identification, parsing, translation)
- MWE discovery in the service of lexicography
- Multiword terms in specialized lexicons
- Representing semantic properties of MWEs in lexicons
- Paving the way towards encoding lexical idiosyncrasies in constructions

¹<http://multiword.sourceforge.net/mwelex2020>

²<http://alt.qcri.org/siglex/>

³<https://elex.is/>

MWE-specific topics

- Computationally-applicable theoretical work on MWEs and constructions in psycholinguistics, corpus linguistics and formal grammars
- MWE and construction annotation in corpora and treebanks
- Processing of MWEs and constructions in syntactic and semantic frameworks (e.g. CCG, CxG, HPSG, LFG, TAG, UD, etc.), and in end-user applications (e.g. information extraction, machine translation and summarization)
- Original discovery and identification methods for MWEs and constructions
- MWEs and constructions in language acquisition and in non-standard language (e.g. tweets, forums, spontaneous speech)
- Evaluation of annotation and processing techniques for MWEs and constructions
- Retrospective comparative analyses from the PARSEME shared tasks on automatic identification of MWEs

We received 25 submissions (14 long and 11 short papers). We selected 6 long papers and 7 short ones. All 13 accepted papers were presented orally. The overall acceptance rate was 52 %.

In addition to the oral sessions, the workshop featured an invited talk that given by Roberto Navigli from Sapienza University of Rome.

The workshop also organized the PARSEME Shared Task on Semi-Supervised Identification of Verbal MWEs (edition 1.2). This was a follow-up of editions 1.0 (2017), and 1.1 (2018). Edition 1.2 featured (a) improved and extended corpora annotated with MWEs, (b) complementary unannotated corpora for unsupervised MWE discovery, and (c) a new evaluation methodology focusing on unseen MWEs. Following the synergy with Elexis, our aim was to foster the development of unsupervised methods for MWE lexicon induction, which in turn can be used for identification.

Seven teams submitted 9 system results to the shared task (some teams made 2 submissions): 2 to the closed track (where only the data provided by the organizers could be used on input) and 7 to the open track (where external data were also allowed). Out of these 9 results, 4 covered all 14 languages for which data were made available by the organizers. Six teams also submitted systems description papers, all of which were accepted and presented orally.

We are grateful to the paper authors for their valuable contributions, the members of the Program Committee for their thorough and timely reviews, all members of the organizing committee for the fruitful collaboration, and all the workshop participants for their interest in this event. Our thanks also go to the COLING 2020 organizers for their support, as well as to SIGLEX and ELEXIS for their endorsement.

Stella Markantonatou, John McCrae, Jelena Mitrović, Carole Tiberiu, Carlos Ramisch, Ashwini Vaidya, Petya Osenova, Agata Savary

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Eric Wehrli, University of Geneva (Switzerland)
Seid Muhie Yimam, Universität Hamburg (Germany)

Invited Speaker:

Roberto Navigli, Sapienza University of Rome

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Workshop Program

Sunday, December 13, 2020

14:00–14:10 *Welcoming and preparation*

14:10–14:40 *Session 1: MWE Resources and Linguistics*

CollFrEn: Rich Bilingual English–French Collocation Resource

Beatriz Fisas, Joan Codina-Filbá, Luis Espinosa Anke and Leo Wanner

Filling the ___-s in Finnish MWE lexicons

Frankie Robertson

Hierarchy-aware Learning of Sequential Tool Usage via Semi-automatically Constructed Taxonomies

Nima Nabizadeh, Martin Heckmann and Dorothea Kolossa

Scalar vs. mereological conceptualizations of the N-BY-N and NUM-BY-NUM adverbials

Lucia Vlášková and Mojmír Dočekal

14:40–14:50 *Break*

14:50–15:20 *Session 2: Verbal Multiword Expressions*

Polish corpus of verbal multiword expressions

Agata Savary and Jakub Waszczuk

AlphaMWE: Construction of Multilingual Parallel Corpora with MWE Annotations

Lifeng Han, Gareth Jones and Alan Smeaton

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VMWE discovery: a comparative analysis between Literature and Twitter Corpora

Vivian Stamou, Artemis Xylogianni, Marilena Malli, Penny Takorou and Stella Markantonatou

Sunday, December 13, 2020 (continued)

15:20–15:30 *Break*

15:30–16:30 *Session 3: Invited Talk*

Generational or: "How We Went beyond Sense Inventories and Learned to Gloss"

Roberto Navigli

16:30–16:40 *Break*

16:40–17:10 *Session 4: Processing Multiword Expressions*

Multi-word Expressions for Abusive Speech Detection in Serbian

Ranka Stankovic, Jelena Mitrović, Danka Jokic and Cvetana Krstev

Disambiguation of Potentially Idiomatic Expressions with Contextual Embeddings

Murathan Kurfalı and Robert Östling

Comparing word2vec and GloVe for Automatic Measurement of MWE Compositionality

Thomas Pickard

Automatic detection of unexpected/erroneous collocations in learner corpus

Jen-Yu Li and Thomas Gaillat

17:10–17:20 *Break*

Sunday, December 13, 2020 (continued)

17:20–18:00 *Session 5: Shared Task*

Edition 1.2 of the PARSEME Shared Task on Semi-supervised Identification of Verbal Multiword Expressions

Carlos Ramisch, Agata Savary, Bruno Guillaume, Jakub Waszczuk, Marie Candito, Ashwini Vaidya, Verginica Barbu Mititelu, Archana Bhatia, Uxoia Iñurrieta, Voula Giouli, Tunga Gungor, Menghan Jiang, Timm Lichte, Chaya Liebeskind, Johanna Monti, Renata Ramisch, Sara Stymne, Abigail Walsh and Hongzhi Xu

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Sebastian Gombert and Sabine Bartsch

18:00–18:10 *Break*

18:10–19:10 *Session 6: Section reporting, panel discussion*

